

Participant Enrolment CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
Section 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria		
3	Has the participant given informed consent or assent?	Yes No (exclude)
4	Is the participant a member of this household?	Yes No (exclude)
5	Does the participant (or representative) speak English or local language [country specific]?	Yes No (exclude)
6	Does the patient have signs of an undiagnosed infection currently?	Yes (exclude) No
Section 2: Identifiable Participant Information		
7	Participant ID	
8	First name	
9	Surname	
10	Date of Birth	DD/MM/YYYY If incomplete / unknown, go to Q10a
10a	What is the participant's age?	____ yrs
11	Participant Sex	Male Female Prefer not to say
12	Is this form being completed by a guardian or representative of the participant?	Yes No (go to Q13)
12a	Scan the Guardian/ Representative ID	
12b	What is the name of the person completing the form?	
12c	What is the nature of the relationship between person completing the form and the individual in question?	Mother Father Grandparent Aunty/Uncle

		Sibling Cousin
13	What is the relationship of the individual to the household head?	Household head Spouse / partner Mother Father Grandmother Grandfather Aunt/Uncle Brother Sister Son Daughter Friend Other (please specify)
14	What is their tribe?	Chewa Lomwe Yao Ngoni Tumbuka Nyanja Sena Tonga Ngonde Baganda Banyankore Basoga Bakiga Iteso Langi Bagisu Acholi Lugbara Banyoro Batoro Alur Other (specify) Prefer not to say
15	What is their religion?	Christianity (go to Q15a) Islam Hindu Traditional African Beliefs Other (specify) Prefer not to say
15a	Which denomination?	
16	Do you own a Phone?	Yes No (go to Q17)

16a	Phone Number 1	
16b	Is this a smart phone?	Yes No
16c	Do you use WhatsApp on it?	Yes No
16d	Do you own any other phones?	Yes No (go to Q17)
16e	Phone Number 2	
16f	Is this a smart phone?	Yes No
16g	Do you use WhatsApp on it?	Yes No
16h	Do you own any other phones?	Yes No (go to Q17)
16i	Phone Number 3	
16j	Is this a smart phone?	Yes No
16k	Do you use WhatsApp on it?	Yes No
Section 3: Occupational, Household and Travel Information		
Occupation		
17	Do you go to school at the moment?	Yes No (go to Q18)
17a	What type of school do you go to?	Primary Secondary College University Other (specify)
17b	What is the name of the school you go to?	
18	What is your job status?	Paid employee Paid domestic worker Self employed Unemployed (go to Q19) Student (go to Q19) Unpaid family worker Other (specify)
18b	What is your occupation?	Agriculture Domestic Service Unskilled manual Skilled manual Sales and services Clerical Technical / managerial Healthcare

		Other professional Student Other (please specify)
19	Do you work at a school or a college?	Yes No (go to Q20)
19a	What type of school do you work in?	Primary Secondary College University Other (specify)
19b	What is the name of the school that you work in?	
19c	What is your job at the school?	Teacher Teaching Assistant Other (specify)
20	Do you work in healthcare?	Yes No (go to Q21)
20a	What type of place is this?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Christian Health Association of Malawi facility Other (specify)
20b	Where do you work? (name of the healthcare institution)	
20c	What is your job at this health care institution?	Doctor Nurse Cleaner Other (specify)
Residency information		
21	How long have you lived in this household?	>1 year (go to Q22) 6 months - 1 years < 6 months
21a	How many times in the last year have you moved to a new house?	Unknown Once Twice 3 or more
22	How often do you live in this house?	All of the time (go to Q23) Most of the time Some of the time Rarely
22a	Where else do you live?	

22b	How long do you spend at this other house each year?	Less than 1 month 1 month 2 months 3 months 4 months 5 months 6 months or more
22c	How far away is this place from where you currently live?	0-1mile 1-5 mile 5-15 miles 15-100 mile away >100 miles away
22d	What type of area is this house in?	Rural Urban Peri-urban
Travel information		
23	How often do you travel outside of Blantyre / Chikwawa / Hoima / Kampala for work?	Weekly Monthly Yearly Never
24	How often do you visit friends or family outside of Blantyre / Chikwawa/ Hoima / Kampala?	Weekly Monthly Yearly Never
25	How often do you seek healthcare outside of Blantyre / Chikwawa/ Hoima / Kampala?	Weekly Monthly Yearly Never (go to Q26)
25a	What type of place is this?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Christian Health Association of Malawi facility Other (specify)
25b	What were you treated for their most recently?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed)

		Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
25c	Did you receive any antibiotics there?	Yes No (go to Q26)
25d	What antibiotics did you receive?	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
25e	What form was the antibiotic?	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
26	Have you travelled outside of the country in the last year?	Yes No (go to Q27)
26a	Where did you travel to (country name)?	
26b	When did you travel?	DD/MM/YYYY

26c	What was the purpose of this travel?	For work Visiting family or friends Holiday For healthcare Other (specify)
26d	Have you travelled anywhere else outside of the country in the last year?	Yes No (go to Q27)
26f	Where did you travel to (country name)?	
26g	When did you travel?	DD/MM/YYYY
26h	What was the purpose of this travel?	For work Visiting family or friends Holiday For healthcare Other (specify)
Section 4: Past Medical History		
27	Does the participant have any medical condition (apart from HIV)?	Yes No (go to Q28)
27a	Select/specify conditions from list. Indicate start data and if known the end date of each condition.	Chronic liver disease Diabetes COPD/Asthma Malignancy (solid organ) Haematological malignancy Chronic kidney disease Cerebrovascular disease Hypertension Anaemia Mental health problem Rheumatic heart disease Ischaemic heart disease Gastritis/gastric ulcer/ GORD Gallstones Other biliary disease Arthritis Congenital malformations Other (specify)
HIV Status		
28	HIV status?	Reactive Non-reactive (go to Q29) Unknown (go to Q29)
28a	Source of HIV status?	Participant Record card

		Other (specify)
28b	Date of HIV test?	DD/MM/YYYY
28c	Is the CD4 count known?	Yes No (go to 28d)
28ci	CD4 source?	Participant Record card Other (specify)
28cii	CD4 count (cells/mm3)	
28ciii	CD4 date?	DD/MM/YYYY
28d	Is the Last viral load known?	Yes No (go to 28e)
28di	Viral load source?	Participant Record card Other (specify)
28dii	Last viral load (copies/ml)	
28diii	Viral Load date?	DD/MM/YYYY
28e	Under HIV follow up?	Yes No (go to 28f)
28ei	Where?	
28f	On ART?	Yes No (go to Q28h)
28fi	ART start date?	DD/MM/YYYY
28fii	ART current regimen? Select if adult or child.	1 (D4T/3TC/NVP) 2 (AZT/3TC/NVP) 3 (D4T/3TC/NVP) 4 (AZT/3TC/EFV) 5 (TDF/3TC/EFV) 6 (TDF/3TC/NVP) 7 (TDF/3TC/LPVr) 8 (AZT/3TC/LPVr) 9 (ABC/3TC/LPVr) 13a (TDF/3TC/Dolutegravir) Other combination (go to Qfiii)
28fiii	Other regimen (tick all that apply)	NVP (Nevirapine) EFV (Efavirenz) LPV/r (Lopinavir/ritonavir) ATV/r (Atazanavir/ritonavir) 3TC (Lamivudine) AZT ABC (Abacavir) FTC (Emtricitabine) D4T TDF (Tenofovir) Dolutegravir Other (specify)
28g	Any previous regimen?	Yes No (go to Q28h)

28gi	Previous regimen start date?	DD/MM/YYYY
28gii	Previous regimen stop date?	DD/MM/YYYY
28giii	Reason for switch?	Clinical failure Immunologic failure Virologic failure Drug reaction Other (specify)
28h	On Cotrimoxazole Preventative Therapy (CPT)	Yes No (go to Q29)
28hi	CPT start date	DD/MM/YYYY
TB Status		
29	Ever treated for TB?	Yes No (go to Q30)
29a	How many times?	
29b	MOST RECENT start date	DD/MM/YYYY
29c	MOST RECENT End date	DD/MM/YYYY
29d	Type of TB	Latent Active: Pulmonary Active: Pleural Active: Meningeal Active: Abdominal Other (specify)
29e	Drugs used	R (Rifampacin) H (Isoniazid) Z (Pyrazinamide) E (Ethambutol) S (Streptomycin) MDR-TB regimen (specify)
Section 5: Medication History		
30	Are they on any medication	Yes No (go to Q31)
30a	Medication name	
30b	Start Date	DD/MM/YYYY
30c	Dose (mg)	
30d	Route	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
30e	Dose frequency	OD (once a day) BD (twice a day) TDS (3 times a day) QDS (4 times a day)

		Other (specify)
30f	Medication ongoing	Yes (go to Q30h) No
30g	End date	DD/MM/YYYY
30h	Are they on any other medication?	Yes (repeat Q30 for each medication) No
Section 6: Health Seeking Behaviour		
31	Where would you seek care if you were ill?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend Christian Health Association of Malawi facility Nowhere Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify)
32	Where would you seek care if you had diarrhoea?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend Christian Health Association of Malawi facility Nowhere Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify)
33	Where would you seek care if you had a fever?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend Christian Health Association of Malawi facility Nowhere Self-treat with left over drugs

		Other (specify)
34	Where would you seek care if you had a persistent cough?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend Christian Health Association of Malawi facility Nowhere Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify)
35	Where would you seek care in you were severely ill?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend Christian Health Association of Malawi facility Nowhere Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify)
Section 7: Health Facility Exposure		
36	Have you been admitted to hospital in the last 6 months (for at least one night)?	Yes No (go to Q37)
36a	When was this?	DD/MM/YYYY
36b	Where was this?	
36c	What were you treated for?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)

36d	How long did you stay at hospital?	1 day 2 days 3 days 4 days 5 days 6 days 7 days 7-14 days >14 days
36e	Were you given antibiotics?	Yes No (go to Q36g)
36f	Which antibiotics (tick all)	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
36g	What form was the antibiotic?	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)

37	Have you stayed in hospital as a guardian in the last 6 months?	Yes No (go to Q38)
37a	When were you in hospital as a guardian?	DD/MM/YYYY
37b	Where were you in hospital as a guardian?	
37c	How long were you a guardian in the hospital for?	1 day 2 days 3 days 4 days 5 days 6 days 7 days 7-14 days >14 days
Section 8: Health questions		
38	Have you been unwell in the last 4 weeks?	Yes No (go to Q39)
38a	What with?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
38b	Did you receive antibiotics for this?	Yes No (go to Q39)
<i>Now I would like to ask you about the antibiotic you took.</i>		
38c	What antibiotic did you take? Tick all (and complete Q38ci-38c for all ticked)	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin

		Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
38ci	What form was the antibiotic	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
38cii	What dose did you take (mg)?	
38ciii	How long did you take it for?	As advised Until cured Until package empty As long as I could afford to One-time treatment Continuously over extended period
38civ	Where did you get the antibiotic from?	Drug shop Traditional healer Pharmacy Referral hospital Other Public Health Facility Private clinic Research clinic/NGO Private hospital Family/friends Other (specify)
38cv	Why did you get it from here?	Cost Location Availability of drugs Recommended by doctor Other (specify)
39	Have you been unwell in the last 3 months (not including the	Yes No (go to Q40)

	episode captured from the last 4 weeks)?	
39a	What with?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
39b	Did you receive antibiotics for this?	Yes No (go to Q40)
<i>Now I would like to ask you about the antibiotic you took.</i>		
39c	What antibiotic did you take? Tick all (and complete Q38ci-38c for all ticked)	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxyethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown

39ci	What form was the antibiotic	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
39cii	What dose did you take (mg)?	
39ciii	How long did you take it for?	As advised Until cured Until package empty As long as I could afford to One-time treatment Continuously over extended period
39civ	Where did you get the antibiotic from?	Drug shop Traditional healer Pharmacy Referral hospital Other Public Health Facility Private clinic Research clinic/NGO Private hospital Family/friends Other (specify)
39cv	Why did you get it from here?	Cost Location Availability of drugs Recommended by doctor Other (specify)
Section 9: Antibiotic usage (uncaptured past and present)		
40	Are you on antibiotics at the moment, that have not been captured already?	Yes No (go to Q41)
40a	Which antibiotic is this?	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin

		Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
40b	Why did you receive this antibiotic	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
40c	What form was the antibiotic	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
40d	What dose did you take (mg)?	
40e	How long did you take it for?	As advised Until cured Until package empty As long as I could afford to One-time treatment Continuously over extended period
40f	Where did you get the antibiotic from?	Drug shop Traditional healer Pharmacy Referral hospital Other Public Health Facility Private clinic

		Research clinic/NGO Private hospital Family/friends Other (specify)
40g	Why did you get it from here?	Cost Location Availability of drugs Recommended by doctor Other (specify)
41	Other than the episodes you have described already, have you had any other antibiotics in the last 6 months?"	Yes No (go to Q42)
41a	Which antibiotic is this?	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
41b	Why did you receive this antibiotic	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat

		Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
41c	What form was the antibiotic	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
41d	What dose did you take (mg)?	
41e	How long did you take it for?	As advised Until cured Until package empty As long as I could afford to One-time treatment Continuously over extended period
41f	Where did you get the antibiotic from?	Drug shop Traditional healer Pharmacy Referral hospital Other Public Health Facility Private clinic Research clinic/NGO Private hospital Family/friends Other (specify)
42	You have completed data collection for this participant. Please thank them for their time.	
43	Staff signature	
44	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY